

Policy brief 3

HUMAN HEALTH RISKS OF NANO- AND MICROPLASTICS (MNPS)

Executive Summary

Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) are pervasive in the environment, found in the air we breathe, the water we drink, and the food we consume. Studies from CUSP indicate that MNPs pose potential risks to human health, including carcinogenicity, reproductive toxicity, respiratory impacts, immunotoxicity, effects on the gut microbiome and endocrine disruption.

Despite advancement in CUSP, significant gaps remain in understanding, significant gaps remain in understanding their biological and health effects and exposure pathways.

This policy brief synthesizes key findings from the European Union’s CUSP research initiative and outlines policy recommendations to mitigate health risks and guide regulatory action.

Introduction

Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) have become a global environmental concern, infiltrating every aspect of human life.

The European Commission’s Research Cluster to Understand the Health Impacts of Micro- and Nanoplastics (CUSP <https://cusp-research.eu>) is now four years into its endeavor to develop new analytical tools, quantify exposures, study the *in-vitro*, *in-vivo*, and human effects, share data, conduct inter-laboratory comparisons, and communicate and disseminate research results on the health impacts of MNPs.

The findings from CUSP have already contributed to filling key knowledge gaps e.g., documenting the potential carcinogenicity, mutagenicity, reproductive toxicity (CMR), immunotoxicity, etc. of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs), primarily *in vitro* using polystyrene. It is clear that MNPs are a public health concern due to the widespread unavoidable exposure of the population to MNPs throughout our lives and the current evidence of hazardous effects, although the health risks remain unclear and the hazards, exposures and risks of individual types of plastics and their specific chemical components still need to be determined. This is particularly the case for the long-term effects on human health¹.

This policy brief explores the health hazards, exposure pathways, and present CUSP frameworks for risk assessment and management, as well as a set of recommendations based on current evidence.

Figure 1: Overview of CUSP main areas of contribution.

¹ CUSP Policy Brief 2 - Micro and Nanoplastics and Public Health: A Reasonable Concern <https://zenodo.org/records/11035612>

RISK ASSESSMENT OF MICRO- AND NANOPLASTICS

CUSP findings on MPN risk assessment

The figure illustrates the **widespread presence and complexity of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs)**, which have been detected by CUSP in air, water, food and human tissues. MNPs, composed of different polymers and additives, can adsorb contaminants and interact with biological systems such as the respiratory tract, immune system and DNA.

Hazard characterisation based on CUSP findings highlights toxicological effects such as oxidative stress and inflammation, although significant knowledge gaps remain regarding long-term, low-dose exposures, combined effects and mechanistic pathways.

Exposure assessment based on CUSP findings confirms the presence of MNPs in environmental and human samples, but reliable data, especially for vulnerable populations, remain scarce.

The **risk assessment frameworks** developed by the CUSP projects integrate hazard and exposure data, but face challenges due to incomplete data sets i.e., information on aggregated exposure of different types of MNPs and all hazard endpoints of regulatory relevance.. Standardisation, policy updates and equitable health interventions are essential to address the risks posed by MNPs.

KEY CUSP FINDINGS

1. Health Hazards

Human exposure to MNPs has been associated with several potential health hazards, as evidenced by emerging research, specially on pristine polystyrene particles. These hazards arise due to MNPs' ability to enter the body through various pathways (i.e., food, air), accumulate in tissues, and interact with biological systems. CUSP findings from *in vitro* experiments on immortalized cell-lines have highlighted key areas of concern including carcinogenicity^{2,3}, inflammation⁴, oxidative stress⁵ and genotoxic responses⁶ linked to certain polymers i.e., polystyrene and PET, particularly when combined, particularly when combined with environmental pollutants (such as nanosilver⁶ and arsenic⁷). We have found that pristine polystyrene particles seem to have minor hazard effects. However, additional research is needed beyond CUSP with a wider range of particles is needed to reach a definitive conclusion. Additionally, the long-term health implications of MNPs remain to be elucidated. Within CUSP, studies on human developmental, respiratory and oral effects have been investigated. Although the results are presently under scientific peer review for publication, the associated experimental work has provided evidence suggesting possible translocation of MNPs across biological barriers including the placenta and lungs¹.

2. Exposure Pathways

CUSP findings provide evidence that humans are exposed to MNPs via various routes, posing potential health risks depending on the exposure pathway. Ingestion occurs primarily through contaminated drinking water, food items, etc., through which MNPs may influence the gut microbiota and impact digestive health. Inhalation of airborne MNPs, both in the general environment and occupational settings, allows particles to reach the respiratory system, potentially causing oxidative stress and inflammation. While dermal contact is less significant, exposure via personal care products does occur, though the likelihood of absorption remains minimal compared to other pathways⁸.

2 Domenech, J. et al. *Mutat Res Rev Mutat Res* 2023 791:108453 Domenech, J. et al. *J. Hazard Mater* 2024 469:134030

3 Domenech, J. et al. *J. Hazard Mater* 2024 469:134030

4 See for instance Dusza, H.M. et al. *Sci Total Environ* 2023 860:160403

5 Alaraby, M. et al. *Sci Total Environ* 2022 842:156923

6 Alaraby, M. et al. *Environ Sci: Nano* 2022 9:1845-1857

7 Barguilla, I. et al. *Int J Mol Sci* 2022 23: 2958

8 Romero-Andrada, A.L. et al. *Arch Bronconeumol* 2023 59(11):709-711; Ramspersger, A.F.R.M. et al. *NanoImpact* 2023 29: 100441; Jiménez-Arroyo, C. et al. *Sci Total Environ* 2023 902:166003

3. Risk Assessment Frameworks

Risk assessment frameworks play a crucial role in evaluating the potential health impacts of MNPs at different stages of their life cycle such as during material research and development; manufacturing and processing; consumer use and product life; and end-of-life.

Implementing distinct frameworks for each life cycle stage ensures a targeted approach, effectively addressing specific challenges and enhancing interventions at critical points. By integrating scientific evidence with regulatory needs, these frameworks help bridge knowledge gaps and prioritize areas requiring action.

Within the CUSP initiative, several risk assessment frameworks have been developed to guide interventions. They draw on different types of plastics, physico-chemical properties, hazards, application and use scenarios and exposure pathways. The *PlasticsFatE* and *POLYRISK*⁹ frameworks assess MNP risks by utilizing polymer property data and (immuno)toxicological evaluations, focusing on minimizing exposure during material development and occupational and public settings. The *IMPTOX* and *AURORA*¹⁰ frameworks analyze MNP exposure impacts on immune responses and early-life health, linking consumer product use and environmental degradation to asthma, allergies, and developmental toxicity risks. Finally, the *PlasticRiskCat* framework identify hazards such as carcinogenicity and reproductive toxicity. Collectively, these frameworks support a comprehensive strategy to mitigate MNP-related risks, guiding safer material innovation, industrial practices, consumer protections, waste management, and environmental policies.

Effective management of the health risks posed by MNPs requires a coordinated and multi-faceted approach¹¹. This entails harmonizing global policies, fostering interdisciplinary research collaborations, and implementing targeted interventions throughout the plastic life cycle to minimize exposure and mitigate risks. There are several actionable steps that policymakers, researchers, industries and civil society organizations can take to mitigate these risks. These recommendations build on current evidence generated in CUSP and emphasize regulatory, research, public health, and precautionary measures to address MNP exposure and its potential impacts on human health.

9 Vogel, A. et al. *Part Fibre Toxicol* 2024 21(1):48

10 Christopher, E.A. et al. *Microplastics and Nanoplastics* 2024 4:13

11 Directorate-General for Environment 2025. *Tackling microplastic pollution with a cross-society approach* https://environment.ec.europa.eu/news/tackling-microplastic-pollution-cross-society-approach-2025-01-16_en?pk_source=ec_newsroom&pk_medium=email&pk_campaign=sfep_news&pk_content=issue613_na1521

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Strengthening Regulatory Frameworks

Establishing a solid regulatory foundation is essential for addressing the health risks posed by MNPs. Regulatory measures should aim at:

- Developing harmonized definitions and standardized methods for detecting and quantifying MNPs in environmental and biological matrices.
- Integrating MNP risk assessments into existing EU regulations, such as REACH, the Drinking Water Directive, Food Safety Regulations (including for food contact materials), and Restriction of microplastics intentionally added to products¹².
- Expanding the scope of the EU Single-Use Plastics Directive on microplastics in consumer products to include broader restrictions beyond items that are most commonly found as marine litter e.g., tea bags and nicotine pouches.

CUSP has supported these outcomes through organizing and leading three interlaboratory comparison studies for the purpose of harmonizing methods for the detection of MNPs. This is a critical first step towards standardization and ensuring that experimental results based on the use of these analytical tools are comparable between different labs across the globe. Standardized methods are also pre-requisites for the enhancement of existing or development of new regulations.

2. Enhancing standard and certification practices for Products and Processes

- Establishing clear criteria for unlikely MNP emission from product during their life-cycle.
- Developing eco-labelling and certification schemes to help consumers identify products with minimal MNP impact.
- Integrating MNP-related sustainability criteria into existing environmental and safety standards for materials and manufacturing.
- Promoting international alignment of standards to facilitate market adoption and compliance across sectors.

3. Advancing Research and Innovation

Investing in research and innovation is pivotal to

Regulatory

addressing the complex health impacts of MNPs. This requires:

- Funding of long-term studies to assess the dose-response relationships and chronic health effects of MNPs.
- Investigating the toxicity of diverse MNPs, including weathered and environmentally relevant particles.
- Developing advanced analytical tools to track MNPs' fate and behavior in the human body and the environment.

CUSP has supported these outcomes through the investigation of human exposure and physiological responses in a variety of different occupational settings. This work has been supported by complex cell-based assays representing different human tissues, where we have measured biomolecular changes over periods of a few hours to several weeks. This has identified that cell-signalling pathways involved in stress and immune responses are turned on in response to different MNPs.

4. Public Health and Awareness Initiatives

Raising public awareness about the risks posed by MNPs to planetary health is essential for fostering informed decision-making and driving behavioral change. These recommendations will serve to initiate efforts:

- Launch educational campaigns to inform consumers about the use of plastics and its environmental consequences including the potential impacts on ecosystems, animals and human health.
- Promote the use of eco-friendly alternatives to reduce MNP pollution.
- Support small and medium enterprises industries with adopting sustainable measures that minimize plastic production and consumption.

CUSP has actively engaged with the wider public through releasing literature, podcasts, and online videos and games. These have been designed to raise awareness of issues, highlight unknowns and provide practical advice on how individual citizens can minimize the release of MNPs through choices they make in their daily lives. Events have also been organized to which representatives of different stakeholder groups: industry, civil society, regulators, policy makers and scientific research have been invited to discuss CUSP research findings in the context of different stakeholder needs.

¹² See for instance Commission Regulation (EU) 2023/2055

5. Precautionary Measures

Given the significant scientific uncertainties surrounding health risks of MNPs, adopting a precautionary approach is critical. Precautionary measures that could be taken while scientific evidence continues to accumulate include:

- Restricting MNPs in products where safer alternatives exist.
- Establishing guidelines to limit MNP exposure via food and water (including from food contact materials and drinking water infrastructure), prioritizing vulnerable groups like children and pregnant women.
- Incentivising industries to adopt best practices that prevent the release of MNPs throughout the product life cycle, from design to disposal.

- Enhancing monitoring and reporting systems to track MNP levels in critical exposure pathways such as sewage sludge used as fertilizer, air, water and food.

CUSP has assessed the utility of different screening methods for MNPs in different exposure settings – importantly highlighting the limitations of some techniques and the difficulty in processing different sample types. We have further identified that MNPs can elicit significant cellular responses, which vary considerably depending on their physicochemical properties, whether they are pristine or aged, and whether they are combined with biological or chemical contaminants.

Projects Specific studies related to MNPs

Working Groups Coordinated efforts across the cluster

CONCLUSION

MNPs present a pressing environmental and public health challenge that demands immediate action. While scientific research has advanced our understanding, significant gaps persist in assessing their short- and long-term biological and health effects. Coordinated efforts between governments, industries, the scientific community and civil society groups are essential to address this global concern.

By implementing robust regulatory frameworks and policies that reduce exposures and the environmental release, investing in research, and raising public awareness, policymakers can mitigate the health impacts of MNPs and pave the way for a sustainable, healthy and future-proof society.

For further information, please visit <https://cusp-research.eu> or contact hello@cusp-research.eu.

Key messages

1. CUSP researchers have documented the potential carcinogenicity, mutagenicity and reproductive toxicity (CMR) of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs), primarily *in vitro* and with polystyrene.
2. Genotoxicity and inflammation have been shown to be good endpoints for assessing the effects of MNPs.
3. The effects of nanoplastics have been observed to be more pronounced than those of microplastics.
4. The main routes of exposure of MNPs to the human body appear to be inhalation and ingestion. Small MNPs have been found to translocate into the blood.
5. Most of the studies conducted to date have been short-term and there is a significant gap in understanding the long-term effects of MNPs on human health. Long-term effects induced by MNPs (genotoxicity, carcinogenesis, reproductive toxicity...) need to be well understood.
6. Further efforts are also needed to better establish dose-response relationships and modes of action. There is a need to move towards effective concentrations rather than applied concentrations.
7. It is important that future studies are carried out on representative MNPs of different chemical compositions and with physico-chemical properties more similar to those found in the environment. Real test materials should be preferred to beads (including real polystyrene and alternative bio-based materials such as polylactic acid).
8. Experimental models capable of recapitulating organ physiology and realistic exposure conditions need to be prioritised for kinetic and effects studies.
9. The synergistic effects of MNPs with other contaminants need to be well investigated.
10. Size and corona influence toxicity and need to be considered in risk assessment and safe-by-design schemes.
11. Potential highly susceptible cells such as stem cells need to be evaluated.
12. The effects of MNPs need to be studied at the molecular level to establish the mode of action of MNPs.
13. Human data on internal exposure and effects is essential. The development of surrogate exposure biomarkers is key to address human biomonitoring studies with large numbers of subjects.

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These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 964827 (AURORA), No. 965173 (IMPTOX), No. 965196 (PlasticHeal), No. 965367 (PlasticsFatE), and No. 964766 (POLYRISK).